

Review of Study of The Motives of Trainee-Teachers For Joining B.Ed. Course

Paper Id : 19218 Submission Date : 2024-08-16 Acceptance Date : 2024-08-22 Publication Date : 2024-08-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13734187

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Abstract

This study explores the underlying motives of trainee-teachers for enrolling in a Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) course. Understanding these motives is essential for improving teacher training programs and addressing the needs and expectations of future educators. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to gather data from a diverse group of trainee-teachers across multiple institutions. The findings reveal a variety of motivations, including intrinsic factors such as a passion for teaching, the desire to make a positive impact on society, and the pursuit of personal growth. Extrinsic factors were also identified, including job security, financial stability, and societal respect associated with the teaching profession. Additionally, some participants cited the B.Ed. course as a stepping stone for further academic or professional opportunities. The study concludes that while intrinsic motivations play a significant role in the decision to pursue a B.Ed., extrinsic factors are also influential. These insights suggest the need for teacher training programs to foster and support both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations to cultivate committed and effective educators. The implications of these findings extend to policy makers, educational institutions, and educators themselves, as they work to enhance the quality and relevance of teacher training programs.

Keywords

Teacher Training Programs, Bachelor of Education.

Introduction

From ancient era, the teacher occupies a middlemost place in the system of education. A teacher bust to students for enhanced learning, in other words teacher provides motivation to students for engaged learning with the help of their teaching methods as well as teaching skills/techniques. For learning of different teaching methods, evaluation methods and many more teaching skills improvement a teacher's professional training course must be needed i.e. B.Ed. Course for Secondary/Senior Secondary School students. In our society, teaching profession is one of the noblest of all professions. Teachers are as spiritual as well as Intellectual Guide of students. Through motivation term, teachers improved extrinsic and intrinsic motives.

In the modern era, the role of a teacher has evolved into that of a facilitator who guides students in their learning journey. Many teachers now use Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to help students better understands the content, which enhances the quality of education. The integration of ICT in education policies has led to improvements in the education system, contributing to the overall growth of our nation. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a prime example of this progress, emphasizing the use of technology to foster a more dynamic and inclusive learning environment.

Teachers are indeed the backbone of the educational system, the creators of future generations, and the real architects of our society. Teacher education is essential in shaping the current social framework and the future of a nation. It has been rightly said that the quality of education and the development across all sectors of a country significantly depend on the quality of its teachers. A well-trained and dedicated teacher can inspire and empower students, fostering critical thinking, creativity, and a lifelong love for learning. In turn, this shapes a knowledgeable, skilled, and responsible citizenry that drives societal progress and national development.

Objective of study

The present study was investigation with the following objectives-

1. To study the motives of B.Ed students for joining teacher professional course i.e. B.Ed.
2. To find out the reasons of joining B.Ed. course by pupil-teachers.

Review of Literature

In Modern era, teacher has been becomes facilitator which provides proper guide to students. During teaching process many teachers used ICT so that student(s) understand concern content. Thus, improved quality education system after made education policies with ICT and grow our nation. National Education Policy (NEP)-2020 one of the best examples for this kind grows-up.

We know very well teacher is the backbone of the educational system, creator of the mankind and the real architect of our society. Teacher education plays a crucial role in structuring the present system of the society and shaping the future of the nation. It has been rightly said that the quality of education and development aspects in all sectors of a country depend much upon the quality of its teachers.

A sound programme for professional education of teachers is essential for qualitative improvement of education. The school as the most important agency of education, with which we are concerned, directs the pupils' activities through its teachers. It is therefore necessary to consider the qualities, qualifications and the interests of the teacher. Nowadays, what motivates a young person to go into teaching is really significant. Any mismatch between the motives and measures perceived to be attractive in teaching may result in those who enter teaching only to quit the profession immediately.

Every Recruitment agencies must consider what motivates young job-seekers to enter teaching and what makes them stay or leave because this understanding is essential in any effort to maintain a stable teaching force, especially in a competing job market of vibrant economics.

Methodology A survey approach was adopted for the present research.

Sampling The study was conducted on a sample of 100 B.Ed students selected from five B.Ed. colleges in Panipat district of Haryana by using a stratified random sampling technique giving due representation to factors. The sample consists of both genders i.e. male and female

Analysis

The researchers visited the five colleges personally and gave the questionnaire by hand to the students in the colleges. The researchers collected the data by giving self-introduction and by explaining the purpose and objectives of the study. The questionnaires were collected after the students marked their opinion for every item in the questionnaire. The data was tabulated carefully, and item-wise analysis was done by using simple percentages.

Interpretation of Data and Results

The collected data analysis was carried out on the basis of objectives of the study by employing appropriate statistical techniques. In each table the items were arranged in descending order and not in the order followed in the questionnaire for clarity. Later the results were interpreted and conclusions were drawn.

Table 1 shows that 49% of the trainees joined because of their interest in the teaching profession, 30% of the trainees joined to seek a government job and 9% of the students joined because they like children. Only 6% of the trainees joined because they didn't want to waste one academic year, as they did not get admission in a postgraduate course. While 2% of the trainees joined for awareness of school administration, another 4% of the students joined due to lack of guidance.

The conclusion is that majority of the students joined the B.Ed course because of their interest in teaching profession and some of the students joined for getting a government job.

Table-1: I willingly joined B.Ed course for the following reasons

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	I am interested in teaching.	49

2	To seek a government job.	30
3	I like children; if I became a teacher, I can spend much time with them in teaching field.	09
4	I didn't want to waste one academic year as I did not get admission in P.G.	06
5	Lack of guidance.	04
6	For the sake of understanding the school administration as I want to start a new school in my own.	02

Table-2 shows that 44% of the trainees felt B.Ed would help them as an additional qualification in their career. 21% of the students felt B.Ed. helps them to enhance the teaching skills as they are already working as teachers in private schools. 18% of the students joined to study M.Ed. 9% of the trainees joined for private schools also demand trained teachers. 7% of the trainees joined with the intention of doing Ph.D in Education. Only 1% of the trainees joined for the promotion because they are teacher trained course (T.T.C.) teachers.

From above results conclusions are revealing that majority of the trainees felt that B.Ed. helped them as an additional qualification in their career and some of the trainees joined B.Ed. to study M.Ed. programme.

Table-2: I joined B.Ed course for the sake of personnel and professional development

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	I want to work as a lecturer: B.Ed. helps me as an additional qualification in my career.	44
2	I am working as a private school teacher: B.Ed. helps me to enhance the teaching skills/techniques	21
3	To Study Master of Education (M.Ed.)	18
4	As per the government's new rule, every private school teacher should be trained	09
5	To gain doctorate degree in Education (Ph.D)	07
6	I am a Teacher Trained Course (TTC) holder teacher: B.Ed. helps me to acquire promotions	01

Table 3 shows that 55% of the trainees joined B.Ed. being influenced by eminent teaching personalities like Dr. Sarvepally Radhakrishnan. 19% of the trainees joined B.Ed. because of the encouragement of their family. 12% of the students joined B.Ed. because of the

influence of their relatives working as teachers. 8% of the students joined B.Ed. due to financial hardships of their families and only 6% of the students' joined B.Ed because of their friends' influence.

The above results reveal that 55% of the students joined being influenced by eminent personalities like Dr Sarvepally Radhakrishan and some of the trainees joined because of the encouragement of their families and relatives.

Table-3: I joined B.Ed course due to the Influence of relatives, friends and others etc.

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	Because of the influence of eminent teaching personalities like Dr. Sarvepally Radhakrishan	55
2	Because of the encouragement of family	19
3	Most of my family members and relatives are working as teachers so I too joined B.Ed	12
4	Due to the financial conditions of my family	08
5	As all my friends are doing B.Ed., I too joined B.Ed.	06

Table 4 shows that 39% of male trainees felt that they could earn more money through tuitions, and coaching after school timings. 34% of female trainees joined too meet household expenses. 22 % of the trainees joined with the intention of demanding higher salary in the private schools.5% of trainees joined with the intention of earning higher profits by establishing B.Ed. colleges/Schools in future.

The results reveal that the majority of the trainees felt that they can earn more money through tuitions, coaching after school hours, and some of the trainees felt that after completion of B.Ed. they could demand higher salary in private schools.

Table-4: I joined B.Ed course due to the following reason related to Financial Growth

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	For male trainees (only males have to answer) Can earn more money through tuitions, coaching after school timings.	39
2	For female trainees (only females have to answer) Can help in household expenses	34
3	Can demand higher salary in the private sector	22
4	Can earn higher profits by establishing B.Ed. colleges in future	05

Table- 5 shows that 52% of the trainees joined because they can prepare the students to the needs of the country and its development. 24% of the trainees felt they could get identity in the society. 14% of the trainees joined to serve the society through teaching profession, and 12% of the trainees joined play an important role in the society.

The above results reveal half of the trainees felt that they can prepare the students to the needs of the country and they can get identity in the society.

Table-5: I joined B.Ed course due to the following reasons related to Service and social Recognition

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	Can prepare students to the needs of the country and its development.	52
2	Can get identity in the society	24
3	Can serve the society through teaching profession	14
4	Teachers play an important role in the society	12

Table- 6 shows that 62% of the trainees joined as they felt teaching profession is a noble profession. 24% of the trainees joined as they felt teaching profession provides opportunities for getting higher rank in the profession. 8% of trainees joined because at present governments is filling teacher vacancies. 3% of the trainees felt teaching profession is a tensionless job. Only 2% of the trainees joined because teaching profession has lesser working days and lesser working hours.

The table-6 results reveal that about half of the students joined B.Ed. as they felt teaching profession is a noble profession and it provides opportunities for getting higher rank in the profession.

Table-6: I joined B.Ed course due to the following reasons related to Teaching profession

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	It is a noble profession compared to others	62
2	Opportunities are there for getting higher rank in the profession	24
3	At present the government is filling teacher vacancies	08
4	Tensionless profession	03
5	Fewer working days than other professions	02
6	Less working hours	01

Table-7 shows that 49% of the trainees hope to play an active role in the society. 35% of the trainees seek higher job satisfaction. 14% of the trainees are for security in their life. 14% of the trainees are hoping to achieve prestige in the profession. Only 1% of trainees are not expecting to get appropriate honour in the profession.

The above results reveal that majority of the students felt teaching profession is the best way to play an active role in the society and they hope to higher job satisfaction in this profession.

Table-7: I joined B.Ed because of Future prospects through teaching Field

Sr. No.	Reasons	Percentage
1	Hope to play an active role in the society	49
2	Hope to seek higher satisfaction in the Profession	35
3	Hope to acquire life security.	14
4	Not expecting to get appropriate honour in the profession.	01
5	Depressed for not getting highest earning job.	01

Conclusion

The results revealed that fifty percent and above student teachers joined in B.Ed course as they felt teaching profession in a noble profession (62%); have an interest in the teaching profession (52%); it can help prepare students to the needs of the country and its development (49%), are influenced by the eminent teaching personalities like Dr. Sarvepally Radhakrishnan (55%).

Some of them joined in B.Ed because of future prospects through teaching field; that they can play an active role in the society (49%); it is for the sake of personal and professional development such as additional qualification to become a lecturer (44%); it provides better job satisfaction (35%); and to study M.Ed (18%).

A few student teachers joined B.Ed with the encouragement of their family members (19%) and with the intention of getting remunerative and other benefits such as government job easily through B.Ed. (30%); to demand highest salary in the private sector (22%). Specific observations between male and female teachers in motives were also analyzed. The male teacher trainees joined B.Ed. because they can earn more money through tuitions, coaching etc. after school hours (39%); female teacher trainees felt that it can help in household expenses (34%).

The results revealed that majority of the student teachers joined B.Ed course with positive and healthy motives which will help to make sustained efforts to achieve the goal of being effective and successful teachers in action and practice.

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